

Bismuth vanadate layers alternated with nanoparticle-doped silicon dioxide layers for one-dimensional multilayer photonic crystals

Francesco Scotognella ^{1,*}

¹ Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129 Torino, Italy

* e-mail address: francesco.scotognella@polito.it

Abstract: Bismuth vanadate is one of most studied materials in the field of photocatalysis due to its high photocatalytic activity. The modulation of its optical properties can be engineered by fabricating photonic crystals in which bismuth vanadate is included. In the present study, bismuth vanadate in the monoclinic clinobisvanite structure has been included in a one-dimensional photonic crystal. Bismuth vanadate layers are alternated with layers on silicon dioxide doped with titanium dioxide nanoparticles and silver nanoparticles. The optical properties of the crystal have been studied by employing the transfer matrix method, taking into account all the refractive index dispersions of the selected materials. The transmission spectra have been studied as a function of the bismuth vanadate layers thickness and the filling factor of titanium dioxide and silver dioxide in the silicon dioxide layers.

Keywords: photonic crystals; bismuth vanadate; effective medium approximation; nanoparticle doped layers.

Introduction

Bismuth vanadate (BiVO_4) is a very interesting material for photocatalysis [1]. The first pioneering works on the photocatalytic activity of BiVO_4 have been reported by Kudo et al. in 1998 [2] and in 1999 [3]. It has been understood that BiVO_4 in the monoclinic clinobisvanite structure shows a remarkable photocatalytic activity [2–5]. There are also other interesting structures of BiVO_4 : In 2014 Cooper et al. have studied the electronic properties of monoclinic sheelite bismuth vanadate [6].

To optimize the employment of BiVO_4 in devices it is very important to know its optical properties. Zhao, Li, and Zou have reported a theoretical analysis in which they have determined the complex dielectric function of monoclinic clinobisvanite BiVO_4 [7]. In 2014 Sarkar, Das, and Chattopadhyay have experimentally measured the complex refractive index dispersion, between 300 and 800 nm, of a monocrystalline monoclinic thin film of BiVO_4 fabricated via radiofrequency sputtering [8].

An interesting way to combine light manipulation and confinement and the optical properties of BiVO_4 is the inclusion of BiVO_4 in a photonic crystal [9]. Photonic crystals are composite materials in which the alternation of two materials with different refractive indexes has a periodicity that is comparable with the wavelength of light [10–12]. Photonic crystals can show such periodicity in one, two and three dimensions [10,13]. The one-dimensional (1D) case is a very flexible way, in terms of fabrication and choice of materials, to fabricate photonic crystals. Very high quality metal oxide-based 1D photonic crystals have been fabricated via radiofrequency sputtering [14]. Via spin coating it is possible to fabricate 1D photonic crystals with polymers [15–18], sol-gel materials [19], and metal oxide nanoparticles [20–22].

In this work the optical properties of 1D photonic crystals that are composed by layers of monoclinic clinobisvanite BiVO_4 and layers of SiO_2 doped with TiO_2 nanoparticles and Ag nanoparticles have been studied. The transfer matrix method has been employed, taking into account the complex refractive index dispersions of all the materials considered in the structure. The versatility of the 1D crystal has been highlighted by reporting the tunability of the photonic band gap as a function of the thickness of BiVO_4 layers, the filling factors of TiO_2 and Ag nanoparticles in the SiO_2 layers.

Methods

Zhao et al. [7] report the complex function of monoclinic clinobisvanite BiVO₄. In this work, the direction orthogonal to (010) planes has been selected (*b*-axis in Ref. [7]). In this work the (010) direction has been selected since for this direction the imaginary part of the dielectric constant is related to a broader transparency (up to 400 nm). The complex refractive index dispersion \mathbf{n}_{BiVO_4} has been determined by using

$$\mathbf{n}_{real} = \sqrt{\left(\left|\sqrt{\varepsilon_1^2 + \varepsilon_2^2}\right| + \varepsilon_1\right)/2} ; \mathbf{n}_{imag} = \sqrt{\left(\left|\sqrt{\varepsilon_1^2 + \varepsilon_2^2}\right| - \varepsilon_1\right)/2} \quad (1)$$

being ε_1 the real part of the dielectric function and ε_2 the imaginary part of the dielectric function. For the 3 component-layer, a layer of SiO₂ doped with TiO₂ nanoparticles and Ag nanoparticles has been considered. The Maxwell-Garnet theory has been used to determine the effective dielectric function for multi-component systems [23,24]:

$$\varepsilon_{eff} = \varepsilon_{matrix} \frac{1+2\sum_i f_i \frac{\varepsilon_i - \varepsilon_{matrix}}{\varepsilon_i + 2\varepsilon_{matrix}}}{1 - \sum_i f_i \frac{\varepsilon_i - \varepsilon_{matrix}}{\varepsilon_i + 2\varepsilon_{matrix}}} = \varepsilon_{SiO_2} \frac{1+2\left(f_{TiO_2} \frac{\varepsilon_{TiO_2} - \varepsilon_{SiO_2}}{\varepsilon_{TiO_2} + 2\varepsilon_{SiO_2}} + f_{Ag} \frac{\varepsilon_{Ag} - \varepsilon_{SiO_2}}{\varepsilon_{Ag} + 2\varepsilon_{SiO_2}}\right)}{1 - \left(f_{TiO_2} \frac{\varepsilon_{TiO_2} - \varepsilon_{SiO_2}}{\varepsilon_{TiO_2} + 2\varepsilon_{SiO_2}} + f_{Ag} \frac{\varepsilon_{Ag} - \varepsilon_{SiO_2}}{\varepsilon_{Ag} + 2\varepsilon_{SiO_2}}\right)} \quad (2)$$

where f_i is the filling factor of the *i*th material. ε_{eff} is a complex function and the complex refractive index dispersion $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{n}_{real} + i\mathbf{n}_{imag}$ has been determined with the aforementioned procedure. In this work we consider that the materials are spatially separated in agreement with the assumptions of the Maxwell-Garnett theory [25].

ε_{SiO_2} has been determined considering that $\varepsilon_{SiO_2} = n_{SiO_2}^2$ and employing the Sellmeier equation for silicon dioxide taken from Ref. [26]:

$$n_{SiO_2}^2(\lambda) - 1 = \frac{0.6961663\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 0.0684043^2} + \frac{0.4079426\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 0.1162414^2} + \frac{0.8974794\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 9.896161^2} \quad (3)$$

Analogously, ε_{TiO_2} has been determined considering that $\varepsilon_{TiO_2} = n_{TiO_2}^2$ and employing a refractive index dispersion for titanium dioxide taken from Ref. [27]:

$$n_{TiO_2}(\lambda) = \left(4.99 + \frac{1}{96.6\lambda^{1.1}} + \frac{1}{4.60\lambda^{1.95}}\right)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

For the dielectric function of Ag nanoparticles the Drude model has been used [28], in which the real and imaginary part of ε can be written as

$$\varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon_\infty - \frac{\omega_p^2}{(\omega^2 + \Gamma^2)} \quad (5)$$

$$\varepsilon_2 = \frac{\omega_p^2 \Gamma}{\omega(\omega^2 + \Gamma^2)} \quad (6)$$

For silver the used values of high frequency dielectric function ε_∞ and carrier damping Γ are 9.1 eV and 0.018 eV, respectively [28].

The transfer matrix method has been used to simulate the transmission spectra of the photonic crystals [14,29]. The incident light impinges the sample orthogonally with respect to the surface of the multilayer (with the light coming from the substrate, Figure 1a) and the materials that compose the multilayer are considered paramagnetic. The matrix for the BiVO₄ layer is

$$\mathbf{M}_{BiVO_4} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \mathbf{n}_{BiVO_4} \mathbf{d}_{BiVO_4}\right) & -\frac{i}{n_{BiVO_4}} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \mathbf{n}_{BiVO_4} \mathbf{d}_{BiVO_4}\right) \\ -i n_{BiVO_4} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \mathbf{n}_{BiVO_4} \mathbf{d}_{BiVO_4}\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \mathbf{n}_{BiVO_4} \mathbf{d}_{BiVO_4}\right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Where λ is the wavelength and \mathbf{d}_{BiVO_4} is the thickness of the **BiVO₄** layers. The matrix of the silica layers doped with titanium dioxide nanoparticles and silver nanoparticles is

$$\mathbf{M}_{dSiO_2} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \mathbf{n}_{dSiO_2} \mathbf{d}_{dSiO_2}\right) & -\frac{i}{n_{dSiO_2}} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \mathbf{n}_{dSiO_2} \mathbf{d}_{dSiO_2}\right) \\ -i n_{dSiO_2} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \mathbf{n}_{dSiO_2} \mathbf{d}_{dSiO_2}\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \mathbf{n}_{dSiO_2} \mathbf{d}_{dSiO_2}\right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Where d_{SiO_2} is the thickness of the doped SiO_2 layers and n_{dSiO_2} is the effective refractive index of the doped SiO_2 layers determined with Equation 2. The characteristic matrix for the multilayer is

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} m_{11} & m_{12} \\ m_{21} & m_{22} \end{bmatrix} = \prod_{i=1}^N M_{BiVO_4} M_{dSiO_2} \quad (9)$$

With N the number of bilayers ($N=10$ in this study). From the matrix M it is possible to determine the transmission coefficient t and the transmission T :

$$t = \frac{2n_s}{(m_{11}+m_{12}n_0)n_s+(m_{21}+m_{22}n_0)} \quad (10)$$

$$T = \frac{n_0}{n_s} |t|^2 \quad (11)$$

Results and Discussion

The photonic crystals studied are composed by 10 bilayers of $BiVO_4$ and of SiO_2 infiltrated with TiO_2 nanoparticles and Ag nanoparticles. In this work, the nanoparticle-doped silica layer is called $Ag:TiO_2:SiO_2$. From an experimental point of view, the fabrication of silver nanoparticles in silica thin films have been reported, for example, in Refs. [30,31], examples of fabrication of titanium dioxide nanoparticles in silica thin films is reported in [32], while the fabrication of silica thin films co-doped with silver nanoparticles and titanium dioxide nanoparticles is reported in Ref. [33].

Figure 1. a) Sketch of the photonic crystals; b) Transmission spectrum of the $BiVO_4/Ag:TiO_2:SiO_2$ photonic crystal as a function of the thickness of the $BiVO_4$ layers ($f_{TiO_2,Ag} = 0.05$).

In Figure 1b the transmission spectrum of a $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Ag}:\text{TiO}_2:\text{SiO}_2$ photonic crystal as a function of the BiVO_4 layers thickness is shown. The filling factors for the Ag and TiO_2 nanoparticles in the SiO_2 layers are 0.05. The thickness of the $\text{Ag}:\text{TiO}_2:\text{SiO}_2$ layers is 100 nm. By increasing the BiVO_4 layers thickness from 80 nm to 100 nm the red shift of the photonic band gap, initially between 650 nm and 870 nm, is clear. The band gap shift occurs without a remarkable broadening or narrowing in its width. This shift toward red is clearly due to the increase in the optical path of the photonic crystal by virtue of the increased thickness of the BiVO_4 layers [34].

Figure 2. Transmission spectrum of the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Ag}:\text{TiO}_2:\text{SiO}_2$ photonic crystal as a function of the filling factor of the TiO_2 nanoparticles in the $\text{Ag}:\text{TiO}_2:\text{SiO}_2$ layers (the thickness of BiVO_4 layers is 100 nm and $f_{\text{Ag}} = 0.05$).

In Figure 2 the transmission spectrum of the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Ag}:\text{TiO}_2:\text{SiO}_2$ photonic crystal as a function of the filling of the TiO_2 nanoparticles is depicted. The thickness of BiVO_4 layers is 100 nm and $f_{\text{Ag}} = 0.05$. With an increase of the filling factor of the titanium nanoparticles from 0.01 to 0.2 a red shift of the band gap, with a concomitant narrowing, is observable.

Figure 3. Transmission spectrum of the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Ag}:\text{TiO}_2:\text{SiO}_2$ photonic crystal as a function of the filling factor of the Ag nanoparticles in the $\text{Ag}:\text{TiO}_2:\text{SiO}_2$ layers (the thickness of BiVO_4 layers is 100 nm and $f_{\text{TiO}_2} = 0.05$).

In Figure 3 the transmission spectrum of the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Ag}:\text{TiO}_2:\text{SiO}_2$ photonic crystal as a function of the filling of the Ag nanoparticles is shown. The thickness of BiVO_4 layers is 100 nm and $f_{\text{TiO}_2} = 0.05$. Also by increasing the filling factor of silver nanoparticles the red shift of the band gap, concomitant to its narrowing, is significant. With silver nanoparticles, the effect can be obtained with smaller filling factors. Such stronger influence of the silver nanoparticle filling factor in the shift of the photonic band gap edges is highlighted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Spectral positions of the high and low energy edges of the photonic band gaps as a function of f_{TiO_2} and f_{Ag} .

In fact, from Figure 4 it is evident that the concomitant red shift and narrowing results in a negligible shift of the low energy photonic band gap edges (red solid line for titanium dioxide nanoparticle filling factor variation and black dotted line for silver nanoparticle filling factor variation, respectively). With a variation of the filling factor of silver nanoparticles from 0.01 to 0.1 a red shift of 63 nm of the high energy photonic band gap edge has been achieved. This change in the transmission spectrum, due to the change in filling factor of the silver nanoparticles or titanium dioxide nanoparticles, can be explained by the simultaneous change in the optical path of the nanoparticle-infiltrated layers, due to the product of thickness and refractive index, and in the width of the photonic band gap, mainly due to the refractive index contrast [34]. In this work the possibility to use many different parameters to manipulate the photonic band gap can open new opportunities to tune, or enhance, the photocurrent and the photocatalytic activity of BiVO_4 [9].

To better understand the possible interaction between the light absorption of BiVO_4 and the optical properties of the photonic crystal it is possible to study the group velocity v_g in the medium. By taking into account the one-dimensional wave equation for periodic Bloch eigenfunctions it is possible to derive the ratio v_g/c [18,35].

$$\frac{v_g}{c} = \frac{\left(\frac{\alpha+\beta}{n_2+n_1}\right) \sqrt{16n_1^2n_2^2 - \{(n_1+n_2)^2 \cos[2\pi(\alpha+\beta)] - (n_1-n_2)^2 \cos[2\pi(\alpha-\beta)]\}^2}}{(n_1+n_2)^2(\alpha+\beta) \sin[2\pi(\alpha+\beta)] - (n_1-n_2)^2(\alpha-\beta) \sin[2\pi(\alpha-\beta)]} \quad (12)$$

where $\alpha = d_{\text{BiVO}_4} n_2 / \lambda = d_{\text{BiVO}_4} n_{\text{BiVO}_4} / \lambda$ and $\beta = d_{\text{dSiO}_4} n_2 / \lambda = d_{\text{dSiO}_4} n_{\text{dSiO}_4} / \lambda$. Inside the gap v_g is purely imaginary and is related to the evanescent wave inside the photonic crystal. At the edges of the photonic band gap v_g is real but tends to zero, resulting in an enhancement of the absorption of BiVO_4 [36]. With a proper design of the photonic crystal the photocatalytic activity of BiVO_4 can be modulated [9]. In the work of Zhang et al. [9], it is reported that photonic films, and specifically inverted opals, of BiVO_4 give rise to photocurrents, under AM1.5 conditions, more than four times higher than the photocurrents detected with planar BiVO_4 electrodes. The promising result could also be reproduced with the one-dimensional photonic crystals presented in this work. The advantages of one-dimensional photonic crystals are the easier fabrication and the possibility of obtaining very intense photonic band gaps.

Figure 5. Transmission spectrum (blue solid curve) and v_g/c ratio (orange point-dashed curve) of the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Ag}:\text{TiO}_2:\text{SiO}_2$ photonic crystal (the thickness of BiVO_4 layers is 100 nm, $f_{\text{TiO}_2} = 0.05$, and $f_{\text{Ag}} = 0.05$).

Conclusion

Monoclinic clinobisvanite bismuth vanadate is an interesting material due to its high photocatalytic activity. The inclusion of bismuth vanadate in a photonic crystal gives the possibility to combine the light manipulation and confinement thanks to the photonic crystal and the optical properties of BiVO₄. In this work, a one-dimensional photonic crystal in which layers of monoclinic clinobisvanite bismuth vanadate and layers of silicon dioxide doped with titanium dioxide nanoparticles and silver nanoparticles has been engineered. The optical properties of the crystal have been studied employing the transfer matrix method, considering the refractive index dispersions of the selected materials. Parameters like the thickness of the bismuth vanadate layers and the filling factor of titanium dioxide nanoparticles and silver nanoparticles significantly influence the spectral position of the photonic band gap. This study can be interesting in order to modulate and filter the absorption of bismuth vanadate layers, for example with a proper overlap between the bismuth vanadate absorption and the photonic band edges where the group velocity of light is slower.

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